

STEREO PARTICLE TRACKING

Dirk Engelmann, Christoph Garbe, Michael Stöhr, Peter Geißler, Frank Hering, Bernd Jähne

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Abstract

Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV) has become a standard technique frequently applied in flow field diagnostics ([1],[7],[8]). This article presents a novel technique which combines the strength of well known 2-D PTV with stereo calibration and correlation techniques to obtain 3D Lagrangian velocity fields.

The here presented stereo correlation technique is fundamental for 3-D PTV. In addition with a sub pixel precise stereo calibration technique it is possible to reconstruct, timely and spatially resolved, paths of particles representing the flow characteristic.

The stereo correlation technique uses the resulting trajectories from PTV. Therefore 2-D trajectories instead of spatial position for single particles are correlated. This allows to keep the set-up simple with a minimum number of two cameras and also speeds up the 3-D evaluation compared to multiple camera set-ups. First results of flow visualisation with particles and air bubbles are presented.

1 Introduction

Applications in 3-D image processing become more a standard technique in many fields

Author(s): Dirk Engelmann¹, Christoph Garbe², Michael Stöhr³, Peter Geißler⁴, Frank Hering⁵, Bernd Jähne⁶

¹IWR, University of Heidelberg, INF 368, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany

²Institute for Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg, INF 366, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany

³BASF AG, Carl-Bosch-Str. 38, D-67056 Ludwigshafen, Germany

⁴1)

⁵1), now at SAP AG, Walldorf, Germany

⁶1), 2)

according to the technical and algorithmic improvements. Flow dynamics is one of the applications where 3-D aspects govern the physical properties of the system. PTV methods are especially well suited to study dynamical processes. The set-up presented here allows to look to a scale of some 10ths of microns. Compared to the Particle Imaging Velocimetry method (PIV) [5] where vector fields over just one time interval are resolved, the tracking of particles yields the flow field over a larger time domain in Lagrangian coordinates. This set-up is also well suited for multi channel investigations like surface slope or gas concentration measurements at the same measuring volume and the same time. Results of flow dynamics in a wind wave flume¹ and in bubble columns² are presented.

The main steps of the algorithm are shown in Fig. 1. The stereo calibration supplies the parameter set for the standard camera model (section 2.1) used for 3-D PTV. The image sequences of the two cameras are then processed separately to extract the trajectories of particles in two dimensions. Finally the stereo correlation of the trajectories from the two cameras provide the trajectories in three dimensional space. In conjunction with the parameter set of the camera model, the absolute spatial coordinates can be obtained.

2 Geometric Camera Calibration

To obtain quantitative results in digital image processing the geometric camera calibration is an essential part of the measuring procedure and evaluation. Its purpose is to give

¹Heidelberg University wind wave flume [12]

²BASF AG Ludwigshafen

Fig. 1 Steps of the 3-D PTV algorithm

a relation between the 3D world coordinate of an object and its 2-D image coordinates. A geometric camera model describes the projection transformation of a 3D-object onto the 2-D CCD-Sensor of the camera. The quality of the camera calibration is crucial for the accuracy of the stereo triangulation (see section 2.4). Effects not included into the camera model will result in a systematic error.

2.1 The camera model

The camera model \mathbf{F} is the mathematical description of the relation between the 3D world coordinates X and the 2-D image coordinates x :

$$x = \mathbf{F}(X). \quad (1)$$

The simplest model is the pinhole camera model. This model is described by four linear transformations including the 10 parameters of translation \mathbf{T} (3 offsets), rotation \mathbf{M} (3 angles), projection \mathbf{P} (focal length) and scaling S :

$$\mathbf{F} = S \cdot \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{P} \quad (2)$$

An extended model includes also lens distortion. Lens distortion is described by a non-linear correction [6]:

$$\Delta x_i^{(r)} = x_i(k_1 r_i^2 + k_2 r_i^4 + \dots) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta y_i^{(r)} = y_i(k_1 r_i^2 + k_2 r_i^4 + \dots) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta x_i^{(t)} = 2p_1 x_i y_i + p_2(r_i^2 + 2x_i^2) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta y_i^{(t)} = p_1(r_i^2 + 2y_i^2) + 2p_2 x_i y_i \quad (6)$$

$$\text{with } r_i = \sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2} \quad (7)$$

k_1 and k_2 are the parameters for radial (r), p_1 and p_2 for tangential (t) distortion.

2.2 Multimedia geometry

The camera looks through a Perspex window into the water (see Fig. 2). Therefore a multimedia correction seems to be necessary. The light is refracted according to Snellius law. Its effect is described by a displacement from the straight line $\Delta X = X_0 - X_{mm}$. If the geometry of the set-up is known, ΔX is a function of X_w and the location of the camera X_k . Since this function has no analytical solution, ΔX has to be calculated numerically applying Fermat's principle.

Fig. 2 Distortion by multimedia geometry

2.3 Parameter estimation

The non-linearity of the camera model does not allow to compute the parameters in a direct analytical way. Therefore a non-linear

minimisation method (Levenberg-Marquardt-Algorithm) is used. The function to minimise is

$$\text{Res} = \sum_i (x_i - \mathbf{F}(X_i))^2 \quad (8)$$

To avoid the algorithm from getting caught in a local minimum, a choice of proper initial values is critical. This can be guaranteed by neglecting the non-linear part of the camera model (k_1, k_2, p_1 and p_2 set to zero). The parameters of the remaining linear model, determined by a Direct Linear Transform (DLT) [11], yield the initial values.

2.4 Inversion of the camera model

The camera model describes the transformation from world to image coordinates. For the evaluation the inverse relation is of interest - to get world coordinates of an object from its position in the 2-D image.

Because the camera model projects a 3-D point to a 2-D point, the solution of the inversion of the camera model is a line. The intersection of the two lines gives the 3-D position of the object (triangulation problem) [6]. Mainly due to noise error the lines do not exactly intersect, so the midpoint of the minimum distance of the two lines is taken as 'intersection point' (equ. 9). To invert the camera model a numerical method has to be used, because an analytical solution does not exist. For an image point x and a given Z-coordinate Z_0 the world point X to be found is given by the minimum of

$$\varepsilon = |x - \mathbf{F}(X)|_{Z=Z_0} \quad (9)$$

As this function is convex, a gradient-based minimisation routine always converges.

3 Virtual Camera

First the accuracy of two versions of the camera model were compared, with and without multimedia correction taken into account. The quality of the camera model can be quantified by the residue (8).

As shown in table *Comparison of camera models* the model without the multimedia correction yields lower residue and therefore a better result. Taking multimedia correction into account, the exact position of the two cameras is

Comparison of camera models:

camera model	residue in $pixel^2$
without multimedia corr.	0.121
with multimedia corr.	0.325

required. In the camera model the z-coordinate of the camera and the focal length are highly correlated parameters. Therefore the camera position is quite uncertain and the multimedia correction is not exact.

We use the model without multimedia correction because of the better results, and therefore the positions of the cameras are virtual. The actual world coordinates of the cameras are not necessary.

4 Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV)

The aim of particle tracking is to identify and trace particles on each image and to follow them over a sequence of images in time. This results in a trajectory of the particle.

The main processing steps are shown in Fig. 3. Due to the time of exposure, the par-

Fig. 3 Steps of PTV.

ticles are imaged as streak on the CCD chip. The streak length and the grey value correspondent to the average speed and the velocity. A typical streak image is shown in Fig. 4. The first step is to identify the streaks. This either can be done by direct segmentation [4] or using a model function to fit the pixel area constituting a particle. An example model for the intensity (grey value) of a moving particle is a

Fig. 4 Typical streak image of camera one and two.

2D-Gaussian function with a linear movement in time [9].

Region growing segmentation method [10] takes in contrary to pixel oriented methods the local neighbourhood into account. Adjacent regions with similar properties are then connected and therefore enlarge the streak.

The model function method is more precise but results in larger computational costs than the region growing method. We use the region growing method, which is adequate for this segmentation problem.

The identification of streaks is finally done by numbering all the pixel belonging to one streak and results in a label image. The position of a particle is now calculated by the centre of mass of the grey values in the labelled area constituting the streak.

Finally the streaks of the image sequence have to be connected in order to construct the trajectories of the particles. The correspondence problem is solved by finding the overlapping of the enlarged streaks. The enlarging is a result of the region growing method, used for the segmentation, and post processing morphological operations like dilation. If the overlapping criteria does not solve the correspondence uniquely, some restrictions are taken:

- Similarity of streaks: Grey value and size difference of two succeeding streak must be below a certain threshold.
- Continuity of optical flow: Because the grey value and the size of a single streak corresponds to the speed of the particle, the sum s over all pixels is constant (if illumination is homogeneous). The smaller two temporal succeeding streak differ in

s the higher is the probability of correlation.

- Extrapolation of velocity: The closer streaks are found to the extrapolated location the higher probability of correspondence.
- Interpolation of local velocity field: Removing of correspondences for too large deviation from calculated velocity (using Adaptive Gaussian Windowing [2]).

Fig. 5 Trajectories resulting from PTV.

Fig.5 shows a typical example of trajectories as a result of the PTV applied on a sequence of images (sample shown in Fig. 4). For better view just a small number of trajectories are displayed out of 1500.

4.1 Stereoscopic Correspondence

Using a calibrated stereo rig 3D trajectories can be reconstructed from the 2D trajectories by solving the stereoscopic correspondence problem. In order to reconstruct the location of the trajectory in three dimensional space, its image coordinates (x, y) and (x', y') have to be found in both cameras, which will be described in detail in the next sections. From (x, y) and (x', y') it is possible to perform the triangulation with the knowledge gained by calibration (see section 2.4).

4.1.1 The epipolar constraint

The computational efficiency of establishing stereoscopic correspondences is increased

Fig. 6 Construction of the epipolar line in the retinal plane of camera 2 from an image point (x, y) on the retinal plane of camera 1

Fig. 7 The epipolar line for a multi media set-up. The tolerance ϵ is added to compensate for noise and the curvature.

by introducing the epipolar constraint. It is derived from stereoscopic geometry and as such a very strong constraint. As stated in section 2.4, the object has to be located on the outgoing ray of the first camera as can be seen in Fig. 6. This ray is in turn depicted by the second camera as the so called epipolar line. The endpoints of the epipolar line are called epipoles. They are defined by the finite depth range of the probing volume. This constraint is of course symmetric for both cameras.

Due to noise and a small error in determining the camera parameters a certain tolerance ϵ is added to the epipolar line. It will thus be a narrow window in image space as is shown in Fig. 7.

Taking lens distortion and multimedia geometry into account, the epipolar line will deviate from a straight line and be slightly bent. In our set-up this curvature proved to be small enough to be accounted for by the tolerance ϵ . For practical purposes the epipolar line is thus replaced by an epipolar window.

4.1.2 The correlation algorithm

In a first step a list of possibly corresponding candidates is constructed. The candidates obey two constraint:

- the time constraint: corresponding trajec-

tories were tracked at the same time,

- the epipolar constraint: the corresponding trajectory T_2 to trajectory T_1 was found within the epipolar window.

Depending on particle densities these two constraints may suffice to allow a unique solution of the correspondence problem. This may not always be the case as high particle densities are beneficial for high spatial resolutions in visualising flows.

Generally there are four possible outcomes of the correspondence search (see Fig. 8):

- (1) *No correspondences*: To a trajectory T_1 in the first camera no corresponding trajectory T_2 was found in the second image.
- (2) *One to one correspondences*: Exactly one corresponding trajectory T_2 was found for a trajectory T_1 .
- (3) *One to many correspondences*: For a trajectory T_1 multiple trajectories $T_{2,i}$ were found, which in turn correspond all to the same trajectory T_1 .
- (4) *Many to many correspondences*: Multiple trajectory $T_{2,i}$ were found for a trajec-

Fig. 8 Some possible cases that may occur during correspondence search

tory T_1 , whereby $T_{2,i}$ correspond to different trajectories $T_{1,i}$.

In case (1) there exist no corresponding pairs of trajectories for which the triangulation could be performed, thus no world coordinates (X, Y, Z) can be computed. This occurs when a particle is imaged by just one camera. To avoid this case it is important to maximise the overlap of the two camera footprints. Another reason might be that streaks are not segmented and tracked correctly. As a countermeasure the illumination should be homogeneous over the whole visible volume of both cameras.

For (2) the correlation was established and the world coordinates (X, Y, Z) of the trajectory can readily be calculated.

There are two distinct possibilities for (3) to occur. The first one is that the trajectories $T_{2,i}$ do not overlap in the time domain. This may be the case when a streak in the second camera was not segmented correctly over the whole time interval of the trajectory T_1 . The resulting trajectories $T_{2,i}$ are thus generated by the same particle and can be marked as corresponding to T_1 .

The other possibility occurs if the trajectories $T_{2,i}$ overlap at the same point in time. Clearly, this violates the boundary condition that trajectories have to be unique. The trajectories $T_{2,i}$ must thus belong to different particles.

New criteria have to be found to overcome these ambiguities. This possibility is thus akin to (4), where multiple trajectories $T_{2,i}$ were found for a trajectory T_1 , all of which correspond to different trajectories $T_{1,i}$.

4.1.3 Some criteria for resolving ambiguities

A strong constraint to solve the remaining ambiguities is the uniqueness constraint. This constraint states that an object point projected onto the first image should match at most with one image point in the other view. This constraint does not hold for transparent objects over a certain size such as bubbles, where reflections may result in a single image point in one view and in two image points in the other.

For flow visualisation we use a symmetric set-up in respect to illumination with small particles which are rotational symmetric. They may thus be viewed as point object for which the uniqueness constraint may be applied.

For experiments at the bubble column it is of course desirable to make use of this constraint as well. This is achieved by positioning the two cameras in such a way that their retinal planes enclose a small angle of approximately 20° only.

The trajectories are constructed from individually segmented streaks S_i . Invalid segmentation may therefore lead to limitations of the uniqueness constraint as not all streaks $S_{1,i}$

in the first image correlate to streaks $S_{2,j}$ in the second image. This is accounted for by a heuristic threshold value K which is determined by the number of correlated streaks k of the trajectories to non correlated streaks n , or $K = k/n$. If the trajectory T_1 comprises of i streaks $S_{1,i}$ and the trajectory T_2 of j streaks $S_{2,j}$ then the number of correlated streaks k is given by $k = \min(j, i)$ and the number of uncorrelated streaks n by $n = |j - i|$. Therefore the threshold K can be written as $K = \frac{k}{n} = \frac{\min(j,i)}{|j-i|}$

In our set-up we found that the segmentation and subsequent tracking proved to be quite reliable. This makes a high threshold K possible which is set to $K = 4$.

Another possible way to solve the correspondence problem is of statistical nature. We stated above that in real world situations correlated streaks in one image will generally not be found on the epipolar line of the second image exactly due to noise and camera distortion. Therefore the standard deviation σ_d can be calculated for the distance d from all the streaks of correlated trajectories to the epipolar line.

If the two trajectories correspond to each other, the distance d will only be due to the tolerance of calculating the epipolar line. It should roughly be the same for all streaks of the trajectory and accordingly the standard deviation σ_d remains small.

If the two trajectories do not correspond, than d will be proportional to the relative motion of the two tracked particles and σ_d is expected to be much larger than in the other case. This makes it possible to solve some ambiguities by thresholding σ_d . In our experiments σ_d was generally less than 0.5 Pixel for corresponding particles.

5 Experimental set-up

As calibration target for stereo calibration a grid was used. On a plain glass plate (< 100 nm deviation in thickness) an approximately 80 nm thick aluminium metal coating layer was applied in square lines (2.5 mm and 5 mm) by a photographic mask and sputtering technique. For calibration the grid was moved perpendicular to the baseline. In the case of the bubble column, a foil with a printed grid was used.

5.1 The Bubble Column

The set-up of the water-filled bubble column is shown in Fig. 9. Air bubbles in a size range from 3 to 5 mm diameter rise from the bottom to the top. The aim is to detect the paths of the moving bubbles. The two CCD-cameras are positioned in a viewing angle of 30° and parallel to the ground plate. The depth of field is larger than the observed volume. Standard video cameras with a frame rate of 1/50 sec. are used for image acquisition. Precise synchronisation (better than one pixel) of the two cameras is essential for an accurate stereo reconstruction.

Fig. 9 Scheme of the bubble column.

5.2 Flow Visualisation in a Wind Wave Channel

The Heidelberg wind wave flume has a circular shape which avoids boundary effects a linear channel has. This shape is well suited for observation of small scale processes such as capillary waves and related effects close the shear layer appear. The wind is produced by paddles driven by a belt. Due to the wind induced momentum and the circular shape of the channel, a large average speed in direction of wind is induced into the water. A moving bed is installed to compensate the average speed. The light source is mounted on the top, and opposite side of the CCD-cameras. A red-filter reduces the effects of light refraction due to chromatic

Fig. 10 Scheme of the flow visualization

aberration. The CCD cameras look through a transparent bottom (Fig. 10) into the volume of interest and the image acquisition rate is 1/60 frames per second. The observation volume results from the geometry of the two intersecting volumes of the two cameras. Each camera looks at an area of about $(7 \times 6.5) \text{ cm}^2$ and the depth of focus is a few cm (depending on aperture and intensity of the scattered light). The intersecting volume is therefore smaller than that a single camera covers.

6 Results

In Fig. 11 the trajectories of the uprising bubbles can be seen. The paths can be seen as a helix shape [3]. The sequence consists of 350 images and about 300 3D-trajectories were extracted from about 3000 trajectories obtained by PTV.

Fig. 12 shows the trajectories of visualised and tracked particles, representing the flow beneath the shear layer. The sequence of 500 images covers a time interval of 8.3 seconds. Small amplitude ($< 0.5 \text{ cm}$) gravitational waves with little steepness ($< 5^\circ$) can be seen as spirally shaped trajectories.

Our approach is very well suited to trace particles moving in spatial trajectories, whereby

Fig. 11 3D-trajectories of bubbles from bubble column.

Fig. 12 3D-trajectories visualising flow, two different perspectives. Top: Perpendicular to the water surface and parallel to the main direction of flow. Bottom: Perpendicular to the main direction of flow and in a slight angle onto the water surface.

the particle tracking algorithm works up to a typical particle density of 1000 per image and the stereo correlation extracts about 10% – 30% (depending on conditions) of the detected trajectories in two dimensions.

The smaller number of 3-D trajectories

compared to the 2-D trajectories is also due to geometric reduction of the intersecting volume from the two cameras. For example if the angle α enclosed by the two cameras (Fig. 10) is 60° and the depth of focus 4 cm, the maximum intersecting volume is 75% (ideal case) of the volume observed by a single camera. The large α is chosen in favour of a higher resolution in depth (z-direction).

Investigations of flow dynamics close the air-water interface and in a bubble column were successfully performed. If the light intensity is homogenous and constant over time, the 3-D PTV can track particle or bubble trajectories over the whole sequence of images. This is well illustrated by the results gained from the bubble column in Fig. 9.

In case of the flow visualisation in the wind wave channel the situation is more difficult. The number of reconstructed 3-D trajectories is much smaller than extracted by PTV and the length of the trajectories is shorter compared to the bubble column. This is a matter of the higher density, the smaller size and the larger velocity of the particles and therefore increase the number of ambiguities in the correlation step. If the change of steepness is small between succeeding images, which is the case for small amplitude gravitational waves the segmentation and PTV works well to gain a first insight into three dimensional flow pattern close the water surface.

6.0.1 Outlook

To study flow dynamics in a size range of a few mm close wavy interfaces, including capillary waves, the segmentation in 2D has to be improved. The segmentation has to cope with the intensity changes due to refraction. According to Snellius law the waves refracts the light due to the steepness of the water surface. This effect can change the intensity of the scattered light drastically from one to the next image and PTV fails to find trajectories or they have a short length. Also illumination will be improved to gain more homogeneous intensity of light through the water interface to avoid large changes of light intensity due to refraction. One main interest is to extend the flow field studies

to work for larger steepness of gravitational and capillary waves.

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